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Lifelong Learning in Italian Regions

Between 2014 and 2021 it grew on average of 20%

The European Innovation Scoreboard-EIS calculates the value of lifelong learning in Italian regions. The variable takes into consideration the percentage of the population having a age between 25 and 64 years of age who are engaged in permanent learning activities.

Ranking of the Italian regions for Lifelong Learning value in 2021. Friuli-Venezia-Giulia is in the first place for the value of lifelong learning with an amount of 110.10 units, followed by the Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of 109.09 units and from Emilia Romagna with an amount of 105.05 units. In the middle of the standings there are Lombardy with an amount of 91.92 units, followed by Piedmont with an amount of 88.89 units and Sardinia with an amount of 85.86 units. Calabria close the ranking with an amount of 57.58 units, followed by Campania with a value of 53.54 units and Sicily with an amount of 48.49 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by variation of the lifelong learning between 2014 and 2021. Veneto is in the first place for the value of the variation of the value of Lifelong Learning with an amount of 59.68% equal to an amount of 37.37 units, followed From Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount of 45.33% equal to an amount of 34.34 units and from Emilia Romagna with an amount of 38.67% equal to an amount of 29.29 units. In the middle of the standings there are Molise with an amount of 24.19% equal to an amount of 15.15 units, followed by Puglia with an amount of 16.00% equal to an amount of 8.08 units. Sicily close the ranking with an amount of 0.00%, followed by Abruzzo with an amount of -5.26% equal to -4.04 units and Campania with a value of -7.02% equal to an amount of -4.04 units. On average between 2014 and 2021, the value of the lifelong learning grew on an average of 20.90% equal to an amount of 14.55%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified as follows:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Emilia-Romagna, Umbria, Sardinia, Lombardy, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Lazio, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Marche, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Calabria, Puglia Sicily, Molise, Basilicata, Abruzzo.

From the point of view of the median, the following system of the Clusters or C1 isolated with a value of 94.94 and C2 with an amount of 58.58 units. From a geographical point of view, it is a dominance of the regions of cluster 1 with respect to cluster 2 which translates into an event of the north-south gap.

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Analysis network with the use of the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is created below with the use of the Euclidean distance. There is a complex network structure as indicated below or:

- Campania has a connection with Calabria for an amount of 0.54 units;
- Calabria has a connection with Campania for an amount of 0.54 units and with Puglia for an amount of 0.64 units;
- Calabria has a connection with Puglia for an amount of 0.64 units.

The following structures were also identified with simplified networks or:

- Emilia Romagna has a connection with Tuscany for an amount of 0.71 units;
- Liguria has a connection with Lombardy for an amount of 0.64 units;
- Piedmont has a connection with the Aosta Valley for an amount of 0.3 units;
- Sardinia has a connection with Lazio for an amount of 0.67 units.

Prediction with Machine Learning algorithms. A comparison with Machine Learning algorithms is presented below to predict the future value of the Lifelong Learning value in the Italian regions. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining part was used to carry out the real prediction activity. Algorithms are organized based on the ability to maximize the R-Squared and the reduction of statistical errors MAE, MSE, RMSE. Specifically, we use the following formulas:

- $R^2 = 1 - \frac{\text{SumSquaredRegression}}{\text{TotalSumOfSquares}} = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y}_i)(y_i - \bar{y}_i)}$
- $MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |e_i|}{n}$
- $MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)(Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)$
- $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)(\hat{y}_i - y_i)}$

The following system of algorithms or:

- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 9;
- PNN-Probabilistic neural Network with a payoff value of 11;
- Ann-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 16;
- Tree regression ensemble with a payoff value of 20;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 24;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore, by applying the Random Forest Regression algorithm, it is possible to identify the following predictions for the following countries or:

- Campania with a value of +235.87%;
- Veneto with a value of +137.41%;
- Emilia Romagna with a value of +23.23%;
- Umbria with a variation of +0.89%;
- Marche with a variation of +23.23%;
- Lazio with a variation of +23.23%.

On average, a growth in the value of the lifelong learning equal to an amount of 73.98% is expected.

Conclusions. Overall, between 2014 and 2021 the value of the lifelong learning has grown significantly on average in the Italian regions of an amount equal to a value of 20%. Although a contrast between North and South is evident. In fact, the North has high levels of lifelong learning compared to the value of the South. However, the prediction with the Random Forest Regression algorithm identifies a growing trend of lifelong learning value in the future. The transition to the economy of knowledge requires a commitment by the population in training perches. Permanent training is also necessary to actively participate in political, economic, and social life. Furthermore, permanent training is also necessary to take advantage of the new services that the public administration and companies offer to citizens and consumers due to the growing level of innovativeness.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Lifelong Learning		
Rank	Regioni	2021
1	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	110,10
2	<i>Trentino Alto Adige</i>	109,09
3	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	105,05
4	<i>Umbria</i>	103,03
5	<i>Veneto</i>	100,00
6	<i>Liguria</i>	98,99
7	<i>Toscana</i>	94,95
8	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	91,92
9	<i>Lombardia</i>	91,92
10	<i>Piemonte</i>	88,89
11	<i>Sardegna</i>	85,86
12	<i>Lazio</i>	85,86
13	<i>Molise</i>	77,78
14	<i>Marche</i>	77,78
15	<i>Abruzzo</i>	72,73
16	<i>Basilicata</i>	70,71
17	<i>Puglia</i>	58,59
18	<i>Calabria</i>	57,58
19	<i>Campania</i>	53,54
20	<i>Sicilia</i>	48,49

Variazione Lifelong Learning 2014-2021			
Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Veneto	37,37	59,68
2	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	34,34	45,33
3	Emilia-Romagna	29,29	38,67
4	Lombardia	25,25	37,88
5	Liguria	26,26	36,11
6	Valle d'Aosta	24,24	35,82
7	Piemonte	23,23	35,38
8	Umbria	21,21	25,93
9	Molise	15,15	24,19
10	Toscana	15,15	18,99
11	Puglia	8,08	16,00
12	Lazio	10,10	13,33
13	Trentino Alto Adige	11,11	11,34
14	Sardegna	8,08	10,39
15	Basilicata	6,06	9,38
16	Calabria	2,02	3,64
17	Marche	2,02	2,67
18	Sicilia	0,00	0,00
19	Abruzzo	-4,04	-5,26
20	Campania	-4,04	-7,02

Lifelong Learning. Fonte: EIS								
Regione	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 65,66	★ 60,61	★ 79,8	★ 74,75	★ 84,85	★ 79,8	★ 84,85	★ 88,889
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 67,68	★ 60,61	★ 79,8	★ 76,77	★ 78,79	★ 82,83	★ 85,86	★ 91,919
<i>Liguria</i>	★ 72,73	★ 63,64	★ 87,88	★ 72,73	★ 92,93	★ 93,94	★ 91,92	★ 98,99
<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 66,67	★ 66,67	★ 90,91	★ 81,82	★ 93,94	★ 87,88	★ 90,91	★ 91,919
<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 76,77	★ 64,65	★ 83,84	★ 71,72	★ 74,75	★ 61,62	★ 67,68	★ 72,727
<i>Molise</i>	★ 62,63	★ 59,6	★ 70,71	★ 77,78	★ 65,66	★ 71,72	★ 78,79	★ 77,778
<i>Campania</i>	★ 57,58	★ 51,52	★ 58,59	★ 54,55	★ 58,59	★ 63,64	★ 57,58	★ 53,535
<i>Puglia</i>	★ 50,51	★ 48,49	★ 63,64	★ 56,57	★ 63,64	★ 53,54	★ 54,55	★ 58,586
<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 64,65	★ 58,59	★ 74,75	★ 60,61	★ 76,77	★ 72,73	★ 79,8	★ 70,707
<i>Calabria</i>	★ 55,56	★ 54,55	★ 67,68	★ 59,6	★ 57,58	★ 60,61	★ 52,53	★ 57,576
<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 48,49	★ 44,44	★ 52,53	★ 47,48	★ 50,51	★ 51,52	★ 52,53	★ 48,485
<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 77,78	★ 75,76	★ 97,98	★ 78,79	★ 100	★ 85,86	★ 85,86	★ 85,859
<i>Veneto</i>	★ 62,63	★ 57,58	★ 81,82	★ 72,73	★ 85,86	★ 91,92	★ 98,99	★ 100
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 75,76	★ 69,7	★ 112,1	★ 105,1	★ 119,2	★ 106,1	★ 114,1	★ 110,101
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 75,76	★ 66,67	★ 94,95	★ 87,88	★ 101	★ 101	★ 110,1	★ 105,051
<i>Toscana</i>	★ 79,8	★ 69,7	★ 88,89	★ 91,92	★ 104	★ 90,91	★ 101	★ 94,949
<i>Umbria</i>	★ 81,82	★ 84,85	★ 98,99	★ 85,86	★ 104	★ 90,91	★ 93,94	★ 103,03
<i>Marche</i>	★ 75,76	★ 73,74	★ 93,94	★ 74,75	★ 86,87	★ 74,75	★ 79,8	★ 77,778
<i>Lazio</i>	★ 75,76	★ 72,73	★ 89,9	★ 83,84	★ 88,89	★ 90,91	★ 81,82	★ 85,859
<i>Trentino Alto Adige</i>	★ 97,98	★ 101	★ 122,7	★ 118,2	★ 116,2	★ 108,6	★ 111,1	★ 109,091

Metriche degli Algoritmi di Machine Learning per la Predizione					
	ANN	PNN	Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	Random Forest Regression	
R²	0,825977873	0,898008511	-2,2942568	0,963034653	
mean absolute error	0,108517954	0,069937052	0,5029788	0,055971455	
mean squared error	0,022283644	0,011546433	0,3632577	0,005688301	
root mean squared error	0,149277072	0,107454328	0,6027086	0,075420826	
	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression	Simple Regression Tree	
R²	0,787090473	0,904873787	-3	0,380186356	
mean absolute error	0,123596747	0,075161527	0,583334861	0,222417844	
mean squared error	0,025182111	0,010541175	0,474110059	0,081403318	
root mean squared error	0,158688722	0,102670226	0,688556504	0,285312667	
Ranking degli algoritmi per valore della capacità predittiva					
Algoritmo	R ²	Mean absolute error	Mean squared error	Root mean squared error	Somma
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>Linear Regression</i>	2	3	2	2	9
<i>PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network</i>	3	2	3	3	11
<i>ANN-Artificial Neural Network</i>	4	4	4	4	16
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	5	5	5	5	20
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	6	6	6	6	24
<i>Gradient Boosted Trees Regression</i>	7	7	7	7	28
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32